

4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) Frag. 60 + 4Q49 (4QJudg^a)

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The small fragment 4Q1 frag. 60 was added on the plates with 4Q1 fragments in 1958 or 1959, and photographed on PAM 43.006.¹ In the official 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) edition it is included as one of the unidentified fragments, but the editor correctly observed that its script is not identical to that of 4Q1, and that the fragment therefore probably belongs to another manuscript.²

This fragment can indeed be identified as belonging to another manuscript, namely 4Q49 (4QJudg^a), a composite fragment consisting of three contiguous pieces and preserving Judg 6:2-13 (notably without 6:7-10).³ Materially, the fragment hitherto known as 4Q1 frag. 60 joins perfectly to the left side of the upper piece, in lines 2 and 3, of the composite 4Q49 fragment. Textually, the fragment only adds a few more letters, corresponding to the Masoretic text, and already reconstructed by the editor. We can now transcribe lines 2 and 3 as follows:

ובני קדם ויחנו על[י]הם וישחתו את[] יבול הארץ עד בואך עזה ולא ישאירו]	2
בישראל	
מחיה שה שור וח[מו]ר כי הם ומקנזיה[ם יעלו ואהליהם וגמליהם יבאו כדי]	3

for image see next page

¹In the IAA reference system, the fragment is numbered Plate 397, Frag. 25. See the plate image <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-371332> and the fragment image <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-362531>.

²James R. Davila, "1. 4QGen-Exod^a," in *Qumran Cave 4 VII: Genesis to Numbers*, ed. Eugene Ulrich and Frank Moore Cross; Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XII (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1994), 7-30 at 30.

³Julio Treballe Barrera, "49. 4QJudg^a," in *Qumran Cave 4 IX: Deuteronomy, Joshua, Judges, Kings*, ed. Eugene Ulrich and Frank Moore Cross; Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XIV (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1995), 161-64. Barrera refers incorrectly to "two contiguous pieces" (160); the middle piece which joins the two larger pieces is not yet present on PAM 42.475 but added on PAM 43.059. It was this small middle piece which demonstrated that Judg 6:7-10 were not included in this manuscript. Alongside Treballe Barrera's excellent edition, and his earlier article "Textual Variants in 4QJudg^a and the Textual and Editorial History of the Book of Judges," *Revue de Qumrân* 14/54 (1989), 229-45, one may also consult Émile Puech, "Le livre des Juges dans les copies qumraniennes (4Q559 4-6, 1Q6, 4Q49-50-50^a)," *Revue biblique* 124 (2017), 342-68, esp. 344-46.

